

ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR SMALL MASS IMPACT WITH DELAMINATION GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model is presented for small mass impact on orthotropic composite laminates with delamination growth, which typically is caused by runway debris and other small objects. Delamination size, load and deflection history are predicted by extension of an earlier elastic impact model by the author. Comparisons with finite element simulations and experiments are provided.

Keywords: Impact, Delamination, Small mass, Model, Analytical

INTRODUCTION

Impact is a well known concern in composite structures and the effects of impact damage is a major issue in the design of aircraft from composite materials [1-2]. The impact response of plates is governed by the impactor/plate mass ratio, where small mass impactors result in a local response controlled by wave propagation and large mass impactors result in a quasi-static response, Fig. 1 [3].

Figure 1: Comparison between a) large mass and b) small mass impact response

A general model for large mass impact on plates was presented in [4]. A model for small mass impact on quasi-isotropic plates with shearing was presented in [5]. Small mass impact on orthotropic plates without shearing was considered in [6]. This model was later extended to include more general load-indentation relations and shear in an approximate fashion [7], by generalisation of the approach suggested in [5].

The threshold load for a single delamination under large mass (quasi-static) impact conditions was first derived in [8]. An exhaustive derivation with generalisation to an arbitrary number of delaminations was given in [9]. The delamination threshold load for

small mass impact was derived in [10], which also provided an extensive validation and closed form expressions for the resulting threshold impact velocity for delamination.

The delamination threshold load in [9] has been combined with quasi-static impactor-plate models to predict delamination onset and growth and its effect on large mass impact response [4]. A similar analytical model for small mass impact response with delamination growth appears to be lacking and the present paper aims to fill this gap.

THEORY

Loads for delamination onset and growth

The load for growth of n delaminations under small mass impact [10] is given by:

$$F_{dn} = C\pi\sqrt{32G_{IIc}D^*/(n+2)} \quad \text{where } C = 1/\sqrt{1-7\pi^2/216} \approx 1.213 \quad (1)$$

The above delamination load for small mass impact was obtained by multiplying the corresponding load for large mass impact with the factor C , which accounts for the inertial effects during small mass impact. Delaminations during impact initiate in all interfaces, but a detailed analysis demonstrates that the strain energy release rate is slightly non-uniformly distributed through the thickness [4,9]. Thus, delamination growth first occurs in a single interface so that the delamination threshold load F_{dth} at small mass impact is given by:

$$F_{dth} = F_{d1} = C\pi\sqrt{32G_{IIc}D^*/3} \quad (2)$$

This conclusion is supported by extensive experimental evidence both from quasi-static impacts [4,8] and from small mass impacts [10]. Analysis [9] and experimental evidence demonstrate that delamination onset (at F_{d1}) in the most critical interface is followed by more or less uniform delamination growth (at F_{dn}) in all available interfaces.

Impact response model

Consider a plate of thickness h and density ρ impacted by an elastic concentrated mass M with initial velocity V_0 , which results in a contact force F . The displacements w_i and w_p of the impactor and plate mass centres are given by [7]:

$$\begin{aligned} w_i &= V_0 t - \int_0^t F(\tau)(t-\tau)d\tau/M \\ w_p &= \int_0^{t-t_0} F(\tau) \frac{2/\pi}{8\sqrt{mD_n^*}} [\arctan\{(1-\tau/t)/\beta_n\} + 2\beta_n/(1-\tau/t)]d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $m=\rho h$ is the plate mass per unit area, t_0 is a time correction accounting for a finite contact area, β_n is a factor expressing the relative shear mobility, which is a function of the effective bending stiffness D_n^* and shear stiffness S_n^* of orthotropic plates with n delaminations, defined by [10]:

$$D_n^* = D^* / (n+1)^2 \quad S_n^* \approx \sqrt{A_{44}^* A_{55}^*} = \sqrt{K_{yz} G_{yz} h K_{xz} G_{xz} h}$$

where $D^* \approx \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22} (1 + \eta) / 2}$ and $\eta = (D_{12} + 2D_{66}) / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}$ (4)

In the above equation K_{xz} and K_{yz} are shear factors, which in most cases are close to the isotropic shear factor $K \approx 5/6$. The contact between a hemispherical impactor of radius R and plate under a load F and indentation approach α is for Hertzian (elastic) contact governed by the following relations (where indices i and p refer to impactor and plate):

$$\alpha = w_i - w_p = \left(F / k_H^* \right)^{2/3} \quad \text{where } k_H^* \approx k_H = \frac{4}{3} Q_H \sqrt{R}$$

Here $1/Q_H = 1/Q_i + 1/Q_p$ and $Q_k \approx E_{zk} / (1 - \nu_{rzk} \nu_{zrk})$ $k = i, p$ (5)

In the above expressions k_H^* and k_H are the contact stiffnesses for plates with finite and infinite thickness. More accurate expressions for k_H^* and Q_p of the plate may be found in [10]. We now introduce the following dimensionless variables:

$$\bar{\alpha} = \alpha / (TV_0) \quad \bar{w}_p = w_p 8\sqrt{mD^*} / (MV_0) \quad \bar{t} = t/T \quad \bar{t}_0 = k_{tH} \bar{\alpha} \quad k_{tH} = RV_0 \sqrt{m/D^*} / 4$$

$$\lambda_n = (n+1)M / \left(8T\sqrt{mD^*} \right) \quad \beta_n = \sqrt{mD^*} / \left[(n+1)S^*T \right] \quad \text{where } T = \left[M / \left(k_\alpha \sqrt{V_0} \right) \right]^{2/5}$$
 (6)

The dimensionless parameters λ_n and β_n represent the relative mobility in bending and shear. The relations Eqs (3)-(5) may then be transformed into the following dimensionless integral equation:

$$\bar{\alpha} = \bar{t} - \int_0^{\bar{t}} \bar{F}(\tau) (\bar{t} - \tau) d\tau - \bar{w}_p \quad \text{where } \bar{F} = \bar{\alpha}^{3/2} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\bar{w}_p = \int_0^{\bar{t}} \bar{F}(\tau) \lambda_n \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\arctan\{(\bar{t} - \tau) / \beta_n\} + 2\beta_n / (\bar{t} + \bar{t}_0 - \tau) \right] d\tau$$
 (7)

The integral equation in Eq. (7) may be discretised and solved in a stepwise manner as shown in [7]. Note, however, that the parameters λ_n and β_n in the current model will change with time as delaminations appear, while they were constants in [7]. Note also that the current model assumes that the parameters λ_n and β_n are fully controlled by the plate properties in the central region with delaminations and that both parameters change instantaneously as delaminations appear. The numerical solution of Eq. (7) was implemented in a short Fortran 95 program, with a typical run time of a few seconds. Two versions of the program were implemented; one threshold version assuming delamination at the peak load, and one which allowed delamination at an arbitrary specified load.

Delamination growth model

For linear elastic materials the change in external work ΔW is twice the change in the strain energy ΔU . The energy balance during dynamic fracture at a constant strain energy release rate G_c may be written as follows:

$$G_c \Delta A = \Delta W - \Delta U - \Delta T = 2\Delta U - \Delta U - \Delta T = \Delta U (1 - \Delta T / \Delta U) \quad (8)$$

where G_c is the critical strain energy release rate and ΔA , ΔW , ΔU and ΔT are the changes in crack surface, external work, elastic energy and kinetic energy. Assuming that the load drops linearly, with an average load F_{av} , during the change in deflection Δw from the undelaminated deflection w_0 to the delaminated deflection w_n with n delaminations we may write the change in elastic energy as follows:

$$\Delta U = \frac{1}{2} \Delta W = \frac{1}{2} F_{av} \Delta w = \frac{1}{4} (F_n + F_0) (w_n - w_0) \quad (9)$$

For small mass impact response due to a point load the ratio between the changes in kinetic energy and elastic energy due to delamination is given by [10]:

$$\Delta T / \Delta U = 7\pi^2 / 216 \quad (10)$$

For growth from an initial undelaminated state the total delamination area A equals ΔA . For plates in flexure delamination takes place under mode II with a critical value G_{IIc} and the delamination area A may thus be approximated by:

$$A = \Delta A = \frac{1}{4} (F_n + F_0) (w_n - w_0) (1 - 7\pi^2 / 216) / G_{IIc} \quad (11)$$

The predicted delamination sizes increase to a certain point in the impact history, which is followed by decreasing values of A . Crack healing is not allowed in the current model, and for this reason the delamination area at a given time was defined by the maximum area up to this time. Table 1 presents the ratio between delamination areas predicted from Eq. (11) using the loads and deflections from FE-simulations with and without delamination, and the delamination area predicted directly by the FE-simulation for various laminates.

Table 1 Ratio of delamination areas predicted from Eq. (11) and from FE analysis

h	2 mm	3 mm	4 mm	5 mm	6 mm
A_{theory}/A_{FE}	0.83	0.98	0.98	1.03	0.86

These results demonstrate that the delamination size can be predicted with acceptable accuracy, provided that the load and deflection histories can be predicted correctly for plates with and without delaminations.

Representation of delaminations in real laminates

Figure 2: Real delaminations and equivalent elliptic delamination

Delaminations in real impacted laminates are not circular, but consist of peanut shaped delaminations of different orientation, Fig. 2 [2]. The superposition of all delaminations is, however, approximately circular in quasi-isotropic laminates and elliptical in orthotropic laminates. Fractography has demonstrated that $\bar{A} \approx 0.30$ defines the ratio between the delaminated peanut shaped area and an inscribing circular area in quasi-isotropic laminates [4]. Delaminations generally appear between all plies of dissimilar orientation, where the size increases with the ply mismatch angle to a maximum at 90° mismatch angle, e.g. +45°/-45° or 0°/90° interfaces [11]. The relative delamination area for a mismatch angle of 45°, when compared to a 90° mismatch angle, is $\bar{A}_{45} \approx 0.60$ [11]. Thus the total delamination area in a laminate may be represented by n^* equivalent elliptical delaminations of area A^* , half-axes a^* and b^* and average diameter d^* :

$$\begin{aligned} A = n^* A^* \quad \text{where } n^* = \bar{A}[\bar{A}_{45} \cdot n_{\Delta 45} + n_{\Delta 90}] \quad \text{and} \quad A^* = \pi d^{*2}/4 \\ \text{with } \bar{A} \approx 0.30 \quad \bar{A}_{45} \approx 0.60 \quad d^{*2} = 4a^*b^* \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Here $n_{\Delta 45}$ is the number of interfaces with 45° mismatch angle and $n_{\Delta 90}$ the number of interfaces with 90° mismatch angle. In most cases typical dimensions of delaminations are not uniform through the thickness. It is common that the delamination zone may be described as truncated cone, with minimum and maximum diameters d_{min} and d_{max} . The ratio ψ between the average and maximum delamination area may then be defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi = A^*/A_{max} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} d_i^2 / d_{max}^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} [d_{min} + (d_{max} - d_{min})i/n]^2 / d_{max}^2 \\ \Rightarrow \psi = \bar{d}_{min}^2 + \left[(\bar{d}_{min} - \bar{d}_{min}^2) + (1 - \bar{d}_{min}^2) (2n+1)/6 \right] (n+1)/n^2 \\ \text{where } \bar{d}_{min} = d_{min}/d_{max} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Combination of Eqs (11) to (13) then result in the following expression for the maximum diameter of a conical delamination zone with n^* equivalent delaminations:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{max} = d^* \sqrt{A_{max}/A^*} = d^* / \sqrt{\psi} \quad \text{where } d^* = \sqrt{4A^*/\pi} = \sqrt{4A/(\pi n^*)} \\ d_{max} = \sqrt{(F_n + F_0)(w_n - w_0) \left(1 - 7\pi^2/216\right) / (\pi\psi n^* G_{IIc})} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

VALIDATION

Numerical validation

To validate the current analytical model it was first compared with finite element (FE) simulations performed at the delamination threshold velocity for a range of homogenous quasi-isotropic plates with a single delamination developing at the midplane. A rigid 3 g ball with 6 mm radius was used to impact 2 to 6 mm thick plates with properties representative of homogenised quasi-isotropic laminates. The properties have been listed in Table 2. The assumed interlaminar shear strength was $\tau_U = 100$ MPa and the delamination work in shear $G_{IIc} = 600$ J/m². Dynamic FE simulations were performed in the explicit code LS-Dyna, using solid elements combined with cohesive elements at the interface. The FE simulations confirmed that delamination growth occurred in pure Mode II, as expected. Further details on the FE model may be found in [10].

Table 2 Plate properties in finite element simulations

$E_x=E_y=E_r$	E_z	$E_x=E_y=E_r$	$\nu_{xy}=\nu_r$	$\nu_{xz}=\nu_{yz}=\nu_{rz}$	Density ρ
56 GPa	10 GPa	4.5 GPa	0.25	0.25	1600 kg/m ³

Figure 3a illustrates the analytically predicted behaviour for a 2 mm laminate with (bold line) and without (thin line) delamination. Delamination onset is reflected by a drop in impact load, and a corresponding increase in deflection. It is noted that the drop in load is significantly larger than the increase in deflections. The difference in load and deflection for the case with and without delamination was used in Eq. (11) to generate predictions of the delamination size.

Figure 3: Predicted response by; a) model with (bold) and without (thin) delamination
 b)-f) model and FE simulations with delamination.
 (solid lines = analytical model, dashed lines = FE-simulation)

Figures 3b-3f show comparisons of the predicted response with delamination by the current analytical model (solid line) and by FE simulations (dashed line). In all cases the delamination growth initiates at the peak (threshold) load and the delamination size quickly approaches a constant finite value. It is worth noting that the test cases correspond to delamination threshold cases which had been found by gradually increasing the impact velocity in the FE simulations until delamination was achieved.

Experimental validation

To experimentally validate the model it was compared with small mass impact experiments with an instrumented spring-activated 10 g aluminium impactor with 6.35 mm tup radius impacting a 6.22 mm HTA/6376C carbon/epoxy laminate at 10 J, Fig. 4a [12]. This energy corresponded to the threshold energy for damage in quasi-static impacts with a 1.5 kg mass, but caused significant delaminations in the small mass impact tests. The $(0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_{6s}$ layup consisted of 23 interfaces with 45° mismatch angle and 24 interfaces with 90° mismatch angle, i.e. $n_{\Delta 45}=23$ and $n_{\Delta 90}=24$. Thus the expected number of equivalent circular delaminations is $n^*\approx 11$. The damage zone was approximately conical with a ratio $\bar{d}_{\min} \approx 0.41$ between minimum and maximum width. The resulting ratio between average and maximum delamination area is $\psi \approx 0.32$. The measured delamination diameter in this experiment was about 4.5 cm.

In the analysis the assumed properties of aluminium were $E_i=70.6$ GPa, $\nu_i=0.3$ and $\rho_i=2790$ kg/m³. Table 3 lists the assumed properties for the HTA/6376C material:

Table 3 Ply properties in experiment

E_1	$E_2=E_3$	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	G_{IIc}	Density ρ
137 GPa	10.4 GPa	5.2 GPa	3.9 GPa	0.30	0.5	600 J/m ²	1620 kg/m ³

Figure 4: Spring activated “mouse trap” instrumented impact rig (a) & FE-simulation (b)

In the experiments the load was measured by a pair of strain gauges on the impactor. One of these appears as a black rectangle on the cylindrical part of the impactor head in the centre of Fig. 4a. The contact force was originally evaluated by multiplying the resulting stress with the cross sectional area and a factor accounting for the difference in the mass above the cross section and the total mass of the impactor. To get a better

understanding of the violent oscillations in measured impact force a dynamic FE analysis of an elastic impactor was recently performed in LS-Dyna for an impact without delamination. The results are shown in Fig. 4b and demonstrate significant differences between the true contact force and the contact force evaluated from the strain gauges. The actual contact force is only 0.52 times the value estimated from the strain gauge signals and does not show the oscillations observed in the strains. The reasons for these differences are not yet fully understood. The corrected strain based force was defined as 0.52 times the nominal value and the general shape shows good agreement with the actual contact force.

A comparison between predictions and experiment for the expected eleven equivalent delaminations ($n^*=11$) is presented in Fig. 5a, where the corrected strain based force has been used. A fair agreement is observed in the general response, although the predicted delamination size is 33% lower than the size measured in experiments.

Cross-sections of similar specimens impacted quasi-statically at 30 J exhibited delaminations in most of the interfaces [12]. The specimens impacted with a small mass at 10 J only had 55% as many delaminations, which were concentrated towards the impacted surface [12]. To study the influence of the number of delaminations the response was also predicted for 55% of 11 equivalent delaminations, i.e. $n^*=6$. A comparison between experiment and predictions is given in Fig. 5b. The influence of the assumed number of delaminations is relatively moderate although the agreement with experimental response and damage is clearly improved, with a predicted delamination size only 23% lower than in the experiments.

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and predicted response; a) $n^*=11$, b) $n^*=6$ (solid line = analytical model, dashed line = experiment)

DISCUSSION

The agreement between the predictions by the current model and FE simulations is surprisingly good, considering the significant simplifications made in the analytical model. These simplifications include a sudden change in plate stiffness and the neglect of influence from the surrounding undelaminated region.

It is, however, noted that even the model with no delamination appears to be slightly too “soft”, which is reflected in larger deflections and lower loads than in the FE simulations. As a result there is a phase shift between the response in the model and the FE simulations. Similar trends have been observed in previous comparisons with experiments, e.g. [6]. The fact that the disagreement also is observed for FE simulations

indicates that the discrepancy is not due to material strain rate effects. A possible cause may be the increased contact stiffness associated with the plate “wrapping” around the impactor, which is not accounted for in the analytical model.

The most important observation from the comparison with the FE simulations at the threshold velocity is the fact that a minimum delamination size is generated as soon as this velocity is reached. This contrasts to quasi-static impacts where the delamination size approaches zero as the delamination threshold velocity is approached [4].

The comparison with experiments on real laminates with multiple plies of different orientation indicates that the assumed number of equivalent circular delaminations is crucial for reliable predictions of the delamination size. In the small mass impact experiment studied here delaminations were not observed in all interfaces, and were primarily located close to the impacted interface. The most probable cause seems to be that the impact velocity was relatively close to the delamination threshold velocity. Similar effects, with a gradual shift from delaminations close to the impacted surface at initiation to fully developed delaminations in all interfaces have been observed in quasi-static impact tests [2]. Delamination growth is promoted by matrix cracks, and the neglect of such cracks may have contributed to the underestimated delamination sizes.

A practical problem is that the oscillations in recorded strains used to determine loads during small mass impact tests make it difficult to distinguish delamination onset and to compare with model predictions. A way to overcome these problems may be selective filtering after an FFT analysis of the spectral content of the signals. Alternatively loads should be measured closer to the point of contact.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the suggested analytical model can be used to predict response and delamination size during small mass impact on plates with delamination onset and growth.

The major weakness of the model is the simplified representation of the complex damage pattern in real laminates. It should be stressed that this weakness is common with most FE simulations of impact. Full consideration of the complex damage requires capability to model growth of all individual matrix cracks and delaminations, which requires separate FE elements with progressive damage modelling for *each* ply.

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